

INTRODUCTION:

SENSORIAL TACTICS IN AN ERA OF SOCIOECOLOGICAL COLLAPSE

Iwona Janicka and Tobias Skiveren

In response to our current socioecological disasters, contemporary philosophers and public intellectuals have offered a plethora of new conceptual tools to help us understand our rapidly transforming world. Think of concepts such as cosmopolitics, planetarity, petro-masculinity, transcorporeality, slow violence, along with the ever-evolving list of “cenes”: Anthropocene, Chthulucene, Capitalocene, Anthrobscene, Thermocene, Necrocene, or Urbanocene, to name only a few.¹ Together, these concepts testify to a collective call for more accurate descriptions of our current condition, while simultaneously showcasing the creative power of contemporary thinkers. Despite this proliferation of concepts, however, the sensorial and affective aspects of our current environmental crises remain understudied, only in recent years grabbing the attention of political theorists, philosophers, and environmental humanists, who are now increasingly recognizing their significance.² And for good reason. The present challenges—and their possible mitigation—are in many ways intimately tied up with questions of perception, affect, and sense-making. We need, this symposium argues, to address such questions in order to address the troubles of our time.

It's hardly an easy task, however, to investigate how our socioecological challenges intersect with sensorial phenomena. After all, such phenomena often work their magic below the threshold of consciousness, eluding our deliberate reflections as well as academic vocabularies. Manifesting themselves as a complex corporal interface, our senses register a wide range of non-conscious perceptions, emotions, and attachments, including those tangled up with the protracted events of global warming, even as this event span over vast planetary and inter-generational

scales.³ While such sensorial impingements are indeed registered, it takes careful attention to render them intelligible. For that, we need new vocabularies.

The stakes are high inasmuch as sensorial phenomena play a crucial role in the cultural dynamics that got us into trouble in the first place. By developing new vocabularies, in other words, we'll gain a language for addressing the perceptual and affective drivers of climate change as well as for developing viable alternatives. This includes tackling the affective appeal of extractivist modes of perception, along with their acquisitive ecstasy, sympathetic void, and phenomenological foregrounding of social and natural environments as resources ready for exploitation. It also includes carving out ways to depart from such sensorial and affective modes of orientation by developing techniques for other ways of sensing the world. Addressing the role of sensation in the Anthropocene, then, is not only about articulating what “we” feel, but also about expanding sensorial repertoires and transforming modes of relating to the world.

The present symposium seizes this task by reflecting on the sensorial, affective, and perceptual dimensions of our socioecological crisis. To that end, it brings together five contributions from scholars currently working on these issues within a diverse set of fields, including ecocriticism, affect theory, political ecology, environmental philosophy, media studies, and the environmental humanities. These contributions, while different in nature, all work within a broad theoretical paradigm sometimes captured under the umbrella term “posthumanities.”⁴ Notwithstanding its different instantiations, this paradigm reconceptualizes human individuals as deeply imbricated in a complex world of affective, material, and discursive forces; and for that reason, it offers a solid basis for studying sensorial and affective phenomena as, not simply affairs limited to the private domain of individual subjects, but as “coarticulations” of larger collective forces as well as fundamental drivers of all human actions.⁵ On this basis, the symposium traces sensorial and affective coarticulations on both individual and collective levels, distinguishing passions that animate collective action from passions that deanimate, isolate, and disempower.

In laying out these dimensions, the symposium advances what could be conceptualized as a set of “sensorial tactics.” With this concept, we’re referring to a deliberate organization of perceptual and affective responses that in various ways work to tackle current socioecological disasters. By helping us sense differently, sensorial tactics, then, stake out affective routes to follow, channeling energies and sensibilities from existing societal conditions into responsibilities worthy of pursuit. We recognize, of course, that such sensorial management is a tricky business. Not only do affective sensibilities, impingements, and trajectories work in unpredictable ways, always one step ahead of our conscious thoughts about them.⁶ Their management could also be taken as an individual affair, leaving the response to, for instance, climate collapse on the shoulders of each individual. And yet, delineating a set of sensorial tactics could also be a way of providing resources to carve out collective change, reorganizing local affective arrangements to afford more apt emotional and perceptual responses. As will be clear, the symposium does this by thinking through at least three sensorial tactics, summarized here as *affective coping strategies*, *post-extractivist sensibilities*, and *non-human sense-making*. Let’s look at these one by one.

As we’ve already noted, living in an age of socioecological disasters isn’t always easy. With these disasters come experiences of irredeemable loss, unevenly distributed across racializing, gendering, and disabling stratifications of power and privilege. In response, the symposium lays out a set of *affective coping strategies* by reflecting on different ways to seize the sense of socioecological collapse. To be sure, these strategies diverge on various points, but they all refrain from lure of naïve optimism. Moving in completely different direction, Martin Savransky speculates about the affective registers available if we take seriously the irreversibility of the planetary condition, arriving ultimately in a rather gloomy stance. Countering the current fascination for hope in critical theory,⁷ Savransky brings together Camus, Nietzsche, and Schopenhauer to develop the concept of *irreverent pessimism*, “an affective disposition that refuses the ongoing subordination of a life to the appeal to another life to come.” Adopting this posture, Savransky claims, enables us to “say no” to the false promise of progress, avoid the

temptations of cruel optimism, and embrace a planetary life without appeal. At stake here is the ability to “carve out a life worth living even in the absence of progressive horizons.”

While pessimism certainly seems alluring in the absence of futures worthy of pursuit, however, it is not the only option. Right next to pessimism sit ironic detachment and dark humor, two other ways one might respond to our current troubles. In her essay on “petroperversity,” Nicole Seymour combines both an exploration of an affective stance that perceives the motifs and events of contemporary petroculture as unintentionally *camp*. Taking her readers on a jaunt through *fossil fuel kitsch* sites in the Long Beach area (Southern California, US), Seymour reflects on the private, zany experiences hovering just below the non-ironic “official” meaning of phenomena such as oil patch liquor t-shirts, oil machinery mosaics, and bridge decommissioning parties. Conceptualizing these kitsch phenomena in dialogue with Susan Sontag, Seymour aims not to “make light of infrastructural violence or environmental injustice,” but to show how adopting a dark ironic eye can work as an affective strategy for “recognizing fossil-fuel ridiculousness,” while at the same time “wringing a little pleasure out of it.”

With this strategy, we’re venturing into the terrain of a second sensorial tactic offered by the symposium. Seymour’s essay aims not only to help one *cope* with a dying world but also to harness a *post-extractivist sensibility* that might contribute to its recovery. By learning to sense petroculture as camp, Seymour claims, we’ll also learn a way of resisting the affective force of fossil fuel extractivism in all its serious, grandiose, masculinist, acquisitive allure. Pursuing post-extractivist sensibilities, then, is about cultivating ways of feeling, sensing, and thinking that subvert and surpass extractivist dispositions and their environmental and social destruction. It’s about developing other attitudes and worldviews than those that primarily seek to take possession and exploit. It’s about “Learning how not to steal”—the blunt title of Alexis Shotwell’s contribution on methodologies beyond extractivism. In this essay, Shotwell reflects on ways in which white settler researchers might resist extractivist logics by adopting alternative affective and epistemic orientations that respect Indigenous sovereignties. “What happens,” she asks, “if I

start from the view that settlerdom-as-extractivism is a structuring condition of possibility for any anti-colonial work I might take up? How can I form relationships with the land, air, water, and other beings of the river valley amongst whom I live and who in various ways support and sustain me? How do such relationships involve and require being in new relation with Algonquin peoples in their relations of care?” Without settling these questions once and for all, Shotwell takes a stab at the tricky task of developing “a pedagogy of anti-extractivism,” turning to two essays by Saidiya Hartman and Dylan Robinson. Reflecting on modes of address in these texts, she delineates a set of devices that invite “we extractivist” to “respect a boundary,” to recognize and abide by wishes to *not* have one’s knowledge extracted, thereby facilitating “a felt shift from extractivist epistemic approaches towards the beginnings of something else.” To develop a post-extractivist sensibility, then, is not simply to leave behind and forget extractivist orientations. As the prefix “post” indicates, it concerns rather the thorough and critical rethinking and subversion of extractivist sensibilities. Seymour’s camp sensibility does this by picking up the zany dimensions of petrocultural environments; Shotwell’s examples ask settler extractivists to respect a “no.”

The third and final sensorial tactic involves the cultivation of *non-human sense-making*. In the environmental humanities and beyond, there’s presently a growing recognition that non-human actors, processes, and entanglements need to be foregrounded in our perceptual apparatuses in order to harness a deeper awareness of our reliance on well-functioning planetary ecosystems.⁸ Less consensus, however, surrounds questions of how to cultivate such non-human sense-making. To explore this question, the symposium turns to scientific data as a means for sensitizing us to such non-human forces. Science, after all, offers useful technological equipment for expanding current phenomenological scopes to include non-human activities and events we might not usually be able to pick up. On the downside, scientific data often take on forms that are inaccessible to a wider public. It typically figures in academic papers, at exclusive conferences, and in complex diagrams, all media that bear little potential to fundamentally reconfigure how the

broader public perceives the world. To broach this conundrum, Jussi Parikka, Paolo Patelli, and May Ee Wong explore moments at which data about the environment “hits the ground” in concrete encounters between specific media and specific bodies, exemplifying how such encounters augment the sensorial capacities of the data-inflicted body. Reflecting on the 2023 Helsinki Biennial *Environmental Audiotour*, they propose “affective data assemblage” as a concept to help us capture how “data,” often taken as an elusive abstraction, links up with complex material arrangements of bodies, technologies, and specific sites that are *felt*. Their concept, then, identifies the ways in which environmental data transform “spatialized modes of sensory engagement which evoke a politics of embodiment and an opportunity for intimacy with the environment.”

And yet, such a focus on scientific data, Anna Krzywoszynska cautions, is not without risks. There’s a danger of being misled by the allure of scientism, tricking us into exaggerating the powers of scientific knowledge. While this objection surely does not apply to Parikka, Patelli, and Wong’s thoughtful piece, it nevertheless points to a potential problem in the work of Bruno Latour, which in many ways, Krzywoszynska shows, accentuates science as a “speaker” for non-human actors and dynamics. Pushing back against this emphasis, Krzywoszynska turns to the work of Hannah Arendt for insights into the importance of grounding politics in a phenomenological *common sense* that emerges from the intersubjectivity of a broader public, not an exclusive group of experts. As a corrective to Latour’s latent scientism, Arendt’s thinking, Krzywoszynska argues, “helps us to ask clearer questions about what kind of (scientific) knowledge and what kind of relations with (scientific) knowledge are needed to respond appropriately to the new human condition” of the Anthropocene.

As might have become clear, the symposium’s essays do not always follow the same line of argument or intellectual style. Indeed, at times they even contradict each other, directing us towards diverging ideas, attitudes, or practices. In combination, however, they provide an array of intellectual resources for developing new sensorial tactics, helping us think through how to

reconfigure perceptual apparatuses in more productive ways. Focusing on affective coping strategies, post-extractivist sensibilities, and non-human sense-making, they stake out alternative ways of perceiving and feeling the world, new forms of response and affective engagement, underscoring the importance of tackling matters of sense and sensation in contemporary attempts to address climate change.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This symposium is a result of the conference “Earth Sensations. Affects, Sensibilities and Attachments in an Era of Climate Change” organised by Iwona Janicka and Tobias Skiveren at Aarhus Institute of Advanced Studies (Denmark) on 13-14th October 2022 and generously funded by Aarhus Institute of Advanced Studies, Aarhus University, the Carlsberg Foundation and the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research, and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 754513 as well as The Aarhus University Research Foundation.

NOTES

¹ See Isabelle Stengers, “The Cosmopolitical Proposal,” in *Making Things Public: Atmospheres of Democracy*, eds. Bruno Latour and Peter Weibel (Cambridge, Mass. and London: MIT, 2005), 994–1003; Dipesh Chakrabarty, “The Planet: An Emergent Humanist Category,” *Critical Inquiry* 46, no. 1 (2019); Cara Daggett, “Petro-Masculinity: Fossil Fuels and Authoritarian Desire,” *Millennium* 47, no. 1 (2018); Stacy Alaimo, *Bodily Natures. Science, Environment, and the Material Self* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2010); and Rob Nixon’s *Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor* (Cambridge MA: Harvard University Press, 2013). For on a useful commented overview of more than eighty of

these terms, see Franciszek Chwałczyk, “Around the Anthropocene in Eighty Names.

Considering the Urbanocene Proposition,” *Sustainability* 12, no. 11 (2020).

² The symposium, then, builds on important work from a wide range of disciplines, counting Glenn Albrecht, “‘Solastalgia’: A New Concept in Health and Identity,” *PAN: Philosophy, Activism, Nature*, no. 3 (2005); William E. Connolly, *Facing the Planetary. Entangled Humanism and the Politics of Swarming* (Durham NC: Duke University Press, 2017); Jane Bennett, *Influx and Efflux. Writing Up with Walt Whitman* (Durham NC: Duke University Press, 2020); Nicole Seymour, *Bad Environmentalism. Irony and Irreverence in the Ecological Age* (Minneapolis: Minnesota University Press, 2018); and Alexa Weik von Mossner, *Affective Ecologies. Empathy, Emotion, and Environmental Narrative* (Columbus: Ohio University Press, 2017).

³ For the concept of the non-conscious, see Katherine Hayles, *Unthought. The Power of the Cognitive Nonconscious* (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 2017).

⁴ Rosi Braidotti, “A Theoretical Framework for the Critical Posthumanities,” *Theory, Culture & Society* 36, no. 6 (2018).

⁵ See for instance Rosi Braidotti, *The Posthuman* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2013); Elizabeth Grosz, *Becoming Undone. Darwinian Reflections on Life, Politics, and Art* (Durham NC: Duke University Press, 2011); Karen Barad, *Meeting the Universe Halfway* (Durham NC: Duke University Press, 2007); Stacy Alaimo, *Bodily Natures. Science, Environment, and the Material Self* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2010); Martin Savransky, *Around the Day in Eighty Worlds Politics of the Pluriverse* (Durham NC: Duke University Press, 2021); Alexis Shotwell, *Against Purity Living Ethically in Compromised Times* (Minneapolis: Minnesota University Press, 2016); Jussi Parikka, *Insect Media. An Archaeology of Animals and Technology* (Minneapolis: Minnesota University Press, 2010). For a thoughtful critique that lays out this paradigm’s relation to Indigenous cosmologies, see Claire Colebrook,

“Anthropocene Objects: The Lifeboat, What Is a Boat?” *Theory & Event* 26, no. 1 (2023).

For the concept a coarticulation specifically, see Iwona Janicka, “Coarticulation: Mutual Transformation in Human and Nonhuman Relations,” *SubStance*, no. 164 (2024).

⁶ Brian Massumi, “The Autonomy of Affect”, *Cultural Critique*, no. 31 (1995). For subsequent debates about this argument, see Margaret Wetherell, *Affect and Emotion. A New Social Science Understanding* (London: Sage, 2012): 60–67; Ben Anderson, *Encountering Affect. Capacities, Apparatuses, Conditions* (Farnham: Ashgate 2014): 5; Clare Hemmings, “Invoking Affect. Cultural Theory and the Ontological Turn,” *Cultural Studies* 19, no. 6 (2005): 565.

⁷ See for instance Christof Mauch, “Slow Hope: Rethinking Ecologies of Crisis and Fear” *RCC Perspectives* 2019, no. 1 (2019); Graeme Wynn, “Framing an Ecology of Hope,” *Environmental History* 25, no. 1 (2020): 2–34; Nicolai Skiveren, “Humor as Hope?: On Critique and Affirmation in Ecological Parody and Satire,” *Environmental Humanities* 16, no. 2 (2024); and Alexa Weik von Mossner, “Wish We Were There: Hope, Desire, and Utopian Community in Contemporary Solarpunk,” *Utopian Studies* 35, no. 2 (2024).

⁸ See for instance Jane Bennett, *Vibrant Matter. A Political Ecology of Things* (Durham NC: Duke University Press, 2010); Timothy Morton, *The Ecological Thought* (Cambridge MA: Harvard University Press, 2010); Maria Puig de la Bellacasa, *Matters of Care. Speculative Ethics in More than Human Worlds* (Minneapolis: Minnesota University Press, 2017); Donna Haraway, *Staying with the Trouble. Making Kin in the Chthulucene* (Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2016); Anna Krzywoszynska and Greta Marchesi, eds., “Conceiving Soils and Humans in the Anthropocene,” special section in *Environmental Humanities* 12, no 1 (2020). For an overview of current pushback against this body of work, see Tobias Skiveren, “New Materialism and the Eco-Marxist Challenge: Ontological Shadowboxing in the Environmental Humanities,” *Environmental Humanities* 15, no. 2 (2023).